

Blind deconvolution and reconstruction of complex point spread functions

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of extreme adaptive optics (AO) systems in the last two decades pushed to unprecedented limits the resolution achievable by ground-based telescopes. Nonetheless, despite the always increasing performances of AO systems, the correction is never perfect, still degrading the images compared to the theoretical limits of the telescope pupil. Using a reference point spread function (PSF) obtained by simulation or by pointing a bright star is not always sufficient due to the random nature of the turbulence. The only solution is thus to extract and reconstruct the AO-PSF directly from the data of interest, a problem known as blind deconvolution. In recent years, marginal approaches emerged, based on a parametric modelling of the AO-PSF with a limited number of physical parameters. These methods correctly grasp the global structure of AO-PSFs (such as full width at half maximum or the AO-cutoff frequency), but they produce perfect PSF that fail at fitting the complex structures of real AO-PSFs such as coherent speckles or multi-lobbed cores in presence of low wind effect or motion blur. With pupil segmented in multiple mirrors and fragmented by the large structures holding the secondary mirror, AO-PSFs of giant telescopes will even more suffer from these effects. To achieve the theoretical performances, it will be necessary to retrieve the 2D image of the AO-PSF in its full complexity. In this work, we present our blind deconvolution method that reconstructs the AO-PSF directly in the data of interest in the presence of sharp-edge objects, such as resolved asteroids, without any prior on the instrument. The PSF faint extensions are reconstructed with a robust penalization optimization, discarding outliers on-the-fly such as cosmic rays or defective pixels. Our methods is successfully applied to a variety of real AO-systems and simulated ELT PSFs.

Keywords: PSF reconstruction ; Blind deconvolution ; Data analysis ; Inverse problem approach ; Physical modelling ; Asteroid

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing size of ground-based facilities, Adaptive optics (AO) is becoming more widespread [16, 30], as the only solution to fully reach the resolution limit of the telescopes without being limited by the atmosphere turbulence that distorts the incident wavefront. For the incoming 30 m-class telescopes, AO is directly embedded in their design such as the M4 of the European Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) [7]. As a consequence all its instruments will thus benefit from AO correction with the objective to deliver a diffraction-limited Point Spread Function (PSF).

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Nonetheless, despite the always increasing performances of AO systems, the correction is never perfect due to intrinsic limitations [13], such as deformable mirror admissible shapes, aliasing of the wavefront sensors, noise propagation, or temporal lag between the applied correction and the turbulence to correct. On longer temporal scales, another limitation is the control of the non-common path aberrations between the AO system on one side, and the science instrument on the other side [33]. The reference wavefront slowly evolves during the acquisitions as the system rotates (mechanical bending) or the temperature changes (thermal dilation). All these issues will be exacerbated for the ELT and its extremely complex pupil : (I) its segmented primary mirror and the large spiders holding its secondary mirror will produce highly structured and complex PSFs [22], (II) the spiders will fragment the measures of the wavefront sensors, isolating each of the pupil sector, leading to the so-called “petalling” problem [20], a worsened version of the “low wind effect” [23] already visible on 8 m-class telescopes that prevents the system to reach its best resolution performances.

In this context, knowing the PSF after an AO system becomes critical if one hope to reach the instrumental limits (photometry, sensitivity, resolution ...) [1]. The most intuitive way is to record a PSF on a reference star prior or after the scientific observation [21], but due to the random nature of AO-PSFs, this is not always sufficient. Thus, the only solution is to retrieve the PSF at the moment of the acquisition of interest. A possible path is to have a look at the AO telemetry: initial methods suggested that not enough information is available for PSF estimation [31], but recent advances in machine learning using years of turbulence parameters on a specific instrument show promising results [18]. This nonetheless implies years to gather the needed dataset and assume that the system is stable enough through its lifetime. As a consequence, the most effective way remains to start from the data of interest themselves, in a process known as blind deconvolution [11, 28, 29]. Marginal approaches [1, 11] which rely on parametric PSF models [3, 10], that depend on a limited number of parameters, efficiently isolate the contributions of the PSF from the object. But these are over-simplistic and cannot reproduce the diversity of AO-PSFs.

More versatile methods than parametric approaches are consequently needed to recover the 2D images of the AO-PSFs in their full complexity. In previous works, see Refs. [2] and [4], we already introduced a blind deconvolution approach in the context of asteroid imaging, with on-sky examples from different instruments. This paper is a direct continuation of these works, with the objective to assess if the method is suited for the complex PSFs of the future ELT. In Sec. 2.1, we briefly recap the alternate blind deconvolution method strategy before introducing a more efficient way to segment the primary in Sec. 2.2, a critical step to split the contributions of the PSF from the object. Then, in Sec. 3, we test the method on ELT PSFs simulated for different scenarios and highlight some on-sky results obtained with the Zurich IMaging POLarimeter instrument [ZIMPOL, 26].

2. METHOD

2.1 Blind Deconvolution Method: a Brief Recap

Figure 1. Forward model of the blind deconvolution problem: the data \mathbf{d} is the convolution of the object \mathbf{o} by the PSF \mathbf{p} , corrupted by a nuisance term \mathbf{n} that is a mixture of read-out noise, photon shot noise, random cosmic rays and possible signal of interest such as moons (red arrows). The data are displayed with a dual linear scale to enhance the bright halo around the primary that can blind the faint neighbouring signals. The asteroid image is a picture of 67P/Churyumov–Gerasimenko by Rosetta (European Space Agency), scaled at a typical angular resolution of the ELT for solar system asteroids. The PSF was generated using TIPTOP [22] in the case of the Multi-conjugate adaptive Optics Relay For ELT Observations [MORFEO, 24], with an important servo-lag error induced by a strong wind.

This section is a short reminder of the blind deconvolution method further detailed in Refs. [2] and [4]. As pictured in Fig. 1, the forward model of the problem classically writes as

$$\mathbf{d} = (\mathbf{o} \star \mathbf{p}) + \mathbf{n}. \quad (1)$$

The image data, \mathbf{d} , is the convolution \star of the extended object, \mathbf{o} , with the long exposure PSF, \mathbf{p} , that combines the telescope and instrument responses and the AO residuals [10] corrupted by a nuisance term \mathbf{n} . This latter encompasses the classical noise terms (detector readout and photon shot noises) as well as model outliers which cannot be explained by the convolution of the PSF with an extended object, such as defective pixels, cosmic rays or moons (red arrows). It is clearly visible that the wind-driven error (green area in the PSF) is responsible of the bright halo surrounding the asteroid in the data. The objectives of the blind deconvolution method are to split \mathbf{o} and \mathbf{p} only from the knowledge of \mathbf{d} without being corrupted by \mathbf{n} , and remove the halo to enhance potentially faint companions.

As detailed in Ref. [2], the extended object, \mathbf{o} and the long exposure PSF, \mathbf{p} Eq. (1) are retrieved by minimizing the regularized cost function $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{o}, \mathbf{p})$:

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{o}}, \tilde{\mathbf{p}}) \leftarrow \underset{\mathbf{o} \geq \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{p} \geq \mathbf{0}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{o}, \mathbf{p}) = \mathcal{D}^{\text{wls}}(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{o} \star \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{w}) + \mu^{\text{obj}} \mathcal{R}^{\text{obj}}(\mathbf{o}) + \mu^{\text{psf}} \mathcal{R}^{\text{psf}}(\mathbf{p}) \right\}. \quad (2)$$

This cost function $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{o}, \mathbf{p})$ is composed of three terms:

The data fidelity term \mathcal{D}^{wls} is the weighted least square difference (wls):

$$\mathcal{D}^{\text{wls}}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \mathbf{w}) \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{x}} w(\mathbf{x}) (\varphi_1(\mathbf{x}) - \varphi_2(\mathbf{x}))^2, \quad (3)$$

The object regularization term $\mathcal{R}^{\text{obj}}(\mathbf{o})$ favours smooth objects with sharp edges by penalising the sparsity of spatial gradients* [8, 25] as classically used in asteroid deconvolution [3, 11, 21, 19, 34]:

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{obj}}(\varphi) \triangleq \sum_{\mathbf{x}} \left[\sqrt{([\nabla_1 \varphi(x)]^2 + [\nabla_2 \varphi(x)]^2 + [\epsilon^{\text{obj}}]^2)} - \epsilon^{\text{obj}} \right], \quad (4)$$

The PSF regularization term $\mathcal{R}^{\text{psf}}(\mathbf{p})$ consists of the classical ℓ^2 -norm on the gradient but applied to the logarithm of the PSF†

$$\mathcal{R}^{\text{psf}}(\varphi) \triangleq \sum_{\mathbf{x}} [\nabla_1 [\ln(\varphi(x))]]^2 + [\nabla_2 [\ln(\varphi(x))]]^2. \quad (5)$$

In the data fidelity term of Eq. (3), the weight term \mathbf{w} is the inverse of the data variance to whiten the residuals $\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{d}^{\text{mod}}$ with

$$\mathbf{d}^{\text{mod}} = \tilde{\mathbf{o}} \star \tilde{\mathbf{p}}. \quad (6)$$

The weight term \mathbf{w} is given by [5, 10, 21]:

$$w(\mathbf{x}) = 1/(\eta d(\mathbf{x}) + v^{\text{ron}}), \quad (7)$$

where v^{ron} is the readout noise and η the factor of the photon noise to convert the intensity into a variance. Finally, in Eq. (2), μ^{obj} and μ^{psf} are hyperparameters to balance the regularizations on the object and the PSF compared to the data fidelity term.

In the following, the PSF \mathbf{p} is initialised with the theoretical diffraction-limited PSF of the equivalent obstructed perfect circular pupil of the telescope‡. Solving Eq. (2) then consists in alternating:

I deconvolving the main extended object $\tilde{\mathbf{o}}$, fixing $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}$,

II reversing the deconvolution paradigm to estimate the PSF $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}$, fixing $\tilde{\mathbf{o}}$. On both unknowns, the physical positivity constraint $\mathbf{o} \geq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{p} \geq \mathbf{0}$ is enforced.

* ∇_1 and ∇_2 correspond to finite difference operators along the two spatial dimensions of the image. $\epsilon^{\text{obj}} > 0$ is a threshold to balance the transition between a ℓ^1 -norm (edge-preserving) and a ℓ^2 -norm (smoothness) while ensuring that Eq. (4) is differentiable at zero.

†The norm on the 2D-gradient ensures a smooth reconstruction, while the logarithm acts as a “dynamic whitening” term regarding the PSF dynamics on several orders of magnitude to enforce variations locally proportional to their intensity.

‡Thus not accounting for the spiders nor the segments: there is consequently no prior on the pupil orientation.

In between each step, the outliers are identified on-the-fly via an iterative reweighted least squares [IRLS, 27] method, based on a robust penalisation [12, 35] enforcing a Cauchy cost function [14] as a robust estimator [15] ρ on the residuals $\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{d}^{\text{mod}}$:

$$\rho(r) \triangleq \frac{\gamma^2}{2} \ln(1 + r^2/\gamma^2) \text{ with } \gamma = 2.385. \quad (8)$$

The robust weight map

$$w^\rho(r) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \rho(r)}{\partial r} = (1 + r^2/\gamma^2)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

is the correction factor to apply to the weights in the least square error of Eq. (3) in the context of IRLS. The outliers are discarded on the fly, using a conservative threshold $\bar{w}^\rho = 50\%$ by updating Eq. (7) while accounting for the data model \mathbf{d}^{mod} :

$$w(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } w^\rho(\mathbf{x}) \leq \bar{w}^\rho \\ 1/(\eta \mathbf{d}^{\text{mod}}(\mathbf{x}) + v^{\text{ron}}) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

2.2 Primary Segmentation

A critical step is hidden in 2.1: the segmentation of the primary from the background. Indeed, the secret of the efficient high spatial frequency split between the object \mathbf{o} and PSF \mathbf{p} lies in the fact that the object has sharp edges. After the object’s deconvolution step, it is thus important to project all pixels outside the asteroid image to 0 to improve the core retrieval by the PSF reconstruction step. In Ref. [2], this was done by applying a threshold on the object. This solution proved to be very effective in the only presence of a blur. Nonetheless, this becomes more difficult in the presence of “ghost” replicates due to PSF core multi-lobbing, for example due to low wind effect [23] or petalling [20], such as in Fig. 2. In this situation, the replicated images also present sharp gradients and potentially intensity values that can be higher (bottom left of the deconvolution) than shadowed parts of the asteroid (top right of the asteroid). Only applying a threshold does not work in this context.

Figure 2. Segmentation strategy: the edges of the object (first line) are identified by maximising the energy of its 2D gradient (second line) contained in the contour. The objects are normalised to the maximal peak of Panel a. The contour is modelled with a spline with 36 knots equally spaced every 10° (dots). The first (red spline) contour estimate (first column) is used to threshold the object below its median value (second column). Then the contour on this clipped object is refined (green spline). For information, the binary object described by the spline contour is given in the third column.

For this work, we developed a new solution based on optimising the “snake energy” [9, 17]. The contour of the asteroid is modelled via a spline of 36 knots (dots in the figure), one placed every 10° from the centre point of view (central isolated dot). This defines a binary object (Fig. 2e) whose gradient energy lies along its edge (Fig. 2f), so-called the “snake”. The knot position has to be adjusted to match the object’s edges.

The centre reference, which should tend towards the barycentre of the object, is first initialised at the centre of the frame (red dot in Fig. 2a). The knots are initially placed at the position of the highest gradient value along

their line of sight (red spline in Fig. 2b). To avoid mistaking a structure at the surface of the asteroid from a ghost image, the median value of the image along this snake is measured, 45 % in the case of Fig. 2a, see colour bar of Fig. 2c. The pixels above this threshold in the asteroid image of Fig. 2a are used to refine the barycentre (green dot). They are then clipped to produce the image of Fig. 2c. The knots are once again displaced onto the highest gradient value of this clipped image (Fig. 2d) and their positions are finally refined by minimising the mean square error between the gradient image of the threshold object (Fig. 2d) and the gradient image of the equivalent binary object defined by the spline (Fig. 2f), resulting in the green solution. To match the gradient dynamic, the binary object is scale by a factor that is fitted along with the knots position, here 20 %, see colour bar of Fig. 2e.

From the figure, it appears that the method successfully avoids to glue to the strong ghost signal at the bottom left of the figure while grabbing again the shadowed area at the top right of the asteroid. Even if the green profile does not seem really physical as an asteroid shape, this is sufficient to dissociate the asteroid from its halo and ghosts images. As seen later in Fig. 3.1, along the blind deconvolution alternate iteration, the asteroid edges get sharper as the ghost images vanish with the correct multi-lobbing of the core and the spline model gets better.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Simulating the ELT

To assess if the method is versatile enough to recover the complex AO-PSFs that will be encountered on the ELT, we applied in this section the proposed blind deconvolution method to simulations that are representative of different situations. For each case, on top of the read-out and photon shot noise, three moons are injected in the noisy data as well as five random cosmic rays and 0.1 % of defective pixels (pepper and salt noise on the figures).

We first started by the perfect case of the diffraction-limited PSF, see Fig. 3. The perfect ELT pupil is displayed on the left. As a reminder, the deconvolution is initialised with the radially symmetric Airy pattern of the obstructed equivalent circular pupil and the deconvolution algorithm does not know where are the spiders, nor that there is a segmented 2D pattern. The fine structures and shadows on the asteroid surface are recovered. The details of the PSF are correctly estimated at a contrast higher than 10^4 , with the diffraction cross due to the spiders very well visible with the correct width. The hexagonal shape of the first Airy rings is also perfectly reconstructed as well as their main speckles. The outliers are successfully identified in the robust weight map and adequately discarded from the fit. They consequently appear in the residual map. The transition between a read-out noise dominated area to a photon noise dominated region at the object location is clearly marked and highlights the fact that the problem cannot be treated as identically distributed noise, as commonly assumed by marginal approaches [11, 21, 19, 34]. Hexagonal ghosts of the edges are noticeable in the residuals but remain marginal, below 0.1 % of the dynamic.

Figure 3. Blind deconvolution method with a perfect ELT pupil (left). Top line: ground truth with three synthetic moons and five cosmic rays. Bottom line: results at the final iteration of the alternate blind deconvolution, displaying the equivalent robust weights, the deconvolved object, the reconstructed PSF and the residuals.

We then tested the case of a pathological petalling [20], see Fig. 4. The differential pistons between the different pupil islands are displayed on the left panel. As seen on the ground truth PSF, such petalling leads to a

multi-lobbed PSF core, with four replicates placed on a rectangle around the main lobe. At the first iteration of the deconvolution, assuming an Airy pattern for the PSF, this leads to the strong ghosts mentioned above in Fig. 2a. The segmentation algorithm manages to disentangle the asteroid from these replicates and the blind deconvolution converges towards a satisfactory solution. The details of the asteroid are recovered with the same accuracy than in the diffraction-limited case. The multi-lobes of the PSF are also accurately reconstructed, as well as the main speckles along the diffraction spikes. Nonetheless, the strong loss of Strehl spreads the PSF pattern of the moons and makes their identification as outliers harder. This has a direct impact on the achievable contrast with a strong self-subtraction, especially on the faintest one (bottom left). Nonetheless, the three moons, hardly seen in the data, are well visible in the residuals.

Figure 4. Blind deconvolution method in the presence of strong petalling (left). See caption of Fig. 3.

The next step is a thought exercise: what would happen if we used the ELT prior its final completion? We randomly removed 25% of its segments, as shown in Fig. 5. As expected, the contrast of the resulting PSF is totally lost, with spatial extensions looking like a random speckle field. Nonetheless, the resolution of the core remains untouched, leading once again to a very accurate deconvolution of the object image. Isolated speckles with a contrast of 10^{-4} are correctly reconstructed in the deconvolved PSF. The self-subtraction on the moon signal is noticeable but under control. Structured patterns are present all over the residuals suggesting that the spatial regularisation of the PSF is too strong. There is a fine and sensitive balance to adjust: a too strong regularisation prevents from estimating the fine PSF details while a too loose regularisation will favour self-subtraction of outliers by producing non-physical structures in the PSF.

Figure 5. Blind deconvolution method in the absence of 25% of the pupil segments (left). See caption of Fig. 3.

We finally applied the method on the realistic case already introduced in Fig. 1 and simulated with TIPTOP [22] for the MORFEO system. As seen in Fig. 6, the PSF is dominated by the servo-lag error that couples with the anisoplanetism and cone effect of the laser guide star system. Once again, the blind deconvolution performs well. The asteroid is indistinguishable from the previous deconvolutions. The recovered size, dynamic and structure of the wind-drive PSF halo (green and yellow) perfectly match the ground truth. Only the closest moon suffers from self-subtraction, as it could be expected. But despite being deeply buried in the halo, it is visible and easily identifiable in the residuals, showing that the halo removal technique is very effective. Let us note that in the absence of high spatial pattern in the PSF, the residuals are better far from the asteroid with no visible structure. Nonetheless, this is not the case close to the edges, where residuals suggest that the sharpness is fully recovered.

Figure 6. Blind deconvolution method in the presence of AO turbulence residuals simulated with TIPTOP (pupil is otherwise perfect, left). See caption of Fig. 3.

We conclude this section insisting on the fact that all the blind deconvolutions were done with the same hyperparameters for the regularisation. This shows the robustness and versatility of the method, which can adapt to a large variety of PSF shapes and turbulence conditions.

3.2 Application to Real Data: SPHERE/ZIMPOL

Of course, there is no ELT on-sky data yet, but it is possible to exercise the method on observations made with existing XAO facilities. ZIMPOL, plugged behind the AO system of the Spectro Polarimetric High-contrast Exoplanet REsearcher [SPHERE, 6], is one of them. Working in the visible, it achieves one of the best resolution currently obtained with ground-based observatories. We tested our deconvolution on (130) Elektra observations obtained in the context of a large program dedicated to Main Belt asteroid imaging [32]. (130) Elektra is the first identified quadruple asteroidal system [3]: its three moons, of different brightnesses and distances, make it a suitable target to test the performances of the outlier automatic rejection and the halo removal.

Figure 7 shows the results after the first (top line) and last (bottom line) iteration of the blind deconvolution algorithm for a given dataset (2019-07-30). A careful look at the object, first deconvolved with the diffraction limited PSF, shows that it seems horizontally smeared, a strong indication of a multi-lobbed PSF induced by low wind effect [23]. Even after one step, the PSF strongly diverged from its diffraction limited initialisation with an Airy circular pattern. Even the innermost Airy ring started to fragment. Something which was not mentioned in Sec. 2.1 is that to speed up the deconvolution and the PSF core recovery, the blind deconvolution is first performed only on a limited region of interest around the object, emphasised by the green dashed square in the figure. Because the asteroid is extended, the PSF is fitted (and retrieved) beyond this limited field of view thanks to the inverse problem approach formalism.

After the alternate optimisation, done on the full field of view, the smearing has gone: the asteroid edges are sharp and details and shadows are visible on the surface. As predicted, the core is multi-lobbed with a shape typical of low wind effect. Once again, the PSF recovery was very effective, the AO cut-off frequency ring as well as its main speckle are well visible. It is also possible to identify the four spikes due to the spider diffraction. The

Figure 7. Blind deconvolution method on a real dataset obtained with ZIMPOL in the presence of low wind effect. First (resp. second) line: results after the first (resp. last) iteration of the alternate blind deconvolution. The green dashed square emphasises the region of interest on which the asteroid and the PSF core are first deconvolved before using the full field of view to fit the faint extensions of the PSF, source of the halo. Red arrows point towards the three moons of (130) Elektra, the brightest being outside the field of view.

two faintest and closes moons[§] are visible in the residuals and correctly discarded by the robust weights. Some defective pixel columns were also discarded.

Figure 8. Comparing the blind deconvolution performances on different epochs for different turbulence conditions on (130) Elektra. First column: zoom on the ZIMPOL reduced data. Second column: state-of-the-art deconvolution. Third column: proposed method. Fourth column: reconstructed PSF. Fifth column: residuals, moons are emphasised with a red arrows. Sixth column: equivalent robust weights.

In Fig. 8, we show acquisitions obtained for different turbulence conditions, compared with the state-of-the-art myopic deconvolution (second column) [11, 21, 32]. The first line (2019-07-30) was obtained the same date than the dataset of Fig. 7, with strong low wind effect. The marginal myopic deconvolution did not manage to erase

[§]As emphasised by the red arrows, the brightest one is outside the reconstructed field of view.

the ghost image, visible on the right side of the asteroid. This ghost image also produced an artificial shade on its left side that could wrongly be interpreted as a geological structure. Our deconvolution produced sharp edges, while recovering details at the surface of (130) Elektra. These details are present on all the deconvolved frames of the acquired sequence (not shown here), suggesting they are real.

The second line of Fig. 8 (2019-08-04) focuses on data obtained during a night with bad seeing. This is clearly visible from the wind driven halo in the reconstructed PSF. As seen above with the simulations, this is associated with a loss of Strehl and thus contrast for the moon recovery. The two faintest ones are barely rejected by the robust weights and at the limit to be seen in the residuals.

The third line of Fig. 8 (2019-08-05) corresponds to data obtained with very good seeing conditions. The reconstructed PSF has a high contrast and a very sharp core. Fine details were recovered on the surface, with a sharp and well defined shadow at the right side of the asteroid. These details were lost by the myopic reference deconvolution. The halo removal was so efficient that it is possible to see the faintest moon very close to the asteroid limb, at a few PSF radii only. A careful look at the residuals show a horizontal zebra structure at the asteroid surface: we are reaching the limits of the ZIMPOL reduction pipeline that interpolates the missing lines of the raw files, a feature of data acquired in non-polarimetric acquisitions.

Finally, Fig. 9 shows in linear scale the reconstructed PSFs (framed in blue) in the presence of low wind effect (2019-07-30), side-by-side with the image of the brightest moon S/2003 (130) 1 (framed in green). Let us insist here that this moon being efficiently rejected by the robust penalisation, it could not be used by the blind deconvolution algorithm to recover the PSF. It is thus a good independent cross-check of the reconstructed PSF core. On all the frames, the estimated PSF perfectly matches the actual PSF, both in terms of dynamic and lobe morphology.

Figure 9. Comparing the reconstructed PSF cores (bottom line) with the images of S/2003 (130) 1 the brightest moon of (130) Elektra obtained on the 2019-07-30.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we briefly reminded the core principle of our blind deconvolution algorithm. In order to efficiently split the object from the PSF contribution in the data, we also introduced a new method based on snake energy optimisation to efficiently segment the object from its surrounding, such as extra-blur, halo, or ghost images. This new solution greatly helps in recovering the PSF core structures, especially in the presence of multiple lobes.

We then applied our method to different simulated ELT PSFs: diffraction-limited PSF, pathological petalling, missing segments, and a MORFEO PSF with strong anisoplanatism. In all the situations, the method managed to retrieve the object fine details as well as the complex structures and high dynamics of the PSFs. All injected outliers, such as defective pixels or cosmic rays, are successfully discarded on-the-fly by the robust penalisation. The faint moons, simulated at different contrasts and distances, are also identifiable within the residuals.

Nonetheless, we noticed that despite the on-the-fly discarding of sharp outliers, these moons can suffer from self-subtraction in the situations where the Strehl is not favourable and that the PSF spreads the signal. Nonetheless, as they still appear in the residuals, they should easily be detected by our method described in Ref. [4]. The next step would be to implement a de-biasing strategy in which moons that are identified as such after the blind deconvolution are discarded from the data before performing again a PSF optimisation. This would prevent any photometry bias, critical to estimate their size.

Finally, the method was tested on real ZIMPOL data but with similar conditions: low wind effect mimicking petalling, wind driven halo mimicking anisoplanatism, and a night with good seeing. The proposed solution outperformed the state-of-the-art reference in all cases, recovering fine details on the asteroid surface. Side-by-side comparisons with the brightest moon, which acts as a ground truth PSF, show that the reconstructed PSFs have the correct dynamic and multi-lobe structure, which are impossible to reproduce with standard blind deconvolution based on parametric models.

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